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Learners Reading Performance: Basis for an Action Plan

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Abstract

This study aimed to assess the reading performance of Grade 1 learners and their impact on academic performance. Employing a descriptive-correlational research design, the investigation focused on describing the demographic profile and its correlation with English performance among Grade 1 learners. The study was set at St. Therese de Avila Learning Center, a well-regarded private school in Iligan City, during the school year 2023–2024. The research targeted 43 Grade 1 learners, comprising 21 males and 22 females. Utilizing statistical tools such as frequency, percentage, mean, standard deviation, and regression analysis, the researchers aimed to identify and analyze the reading performance levels of learners, exploring how these aspects influence academic performance in the English subject. This research provided an opportunity to gain insights into the relationship between reading performance and academic achievement, offering valuable information for educators and policymakers to enhance language education strategies for young learners. Findings revealed a diverse distribution of respondents based on age and gender, with a majority falling into the 6-year age group and a balanced representation of males and females. Learners exhibited notable proficiency in reading performance, with a majority achieving outstanding scores. Academic performance in English also showcased remarkable achievement, with a significant proportion attaining outstanding grades. Regression Analyses underscored critical role of reading performance in predicting academic success in English, informing the Comprehensive English Proficiency Initiative aimed at enhancing learners' English proficiency through targeted strategies and programs.

Keywords: *learners' reading performance, academic performance, assessment, description-correlational*

Introduction

Reading plays a crucial role in a child's early years as it contributes significantly to their development. During this period, children experienced their fastest rate of growth, commonly referred to as "the foundation years." By nurturing certain abilities during these formative years, parents and educators could establish a sturdy groundwork for the child's future. Considered an early advantage in schooling, reading comprehension served as the cornerstone upon which all other academic skills were built. It facilitated language development, expanded world knowledge, and enhanced the comprehension of complex ideas (Escar, 2022).

Success in both school and life hinges on a child's proficiency in reading, writing, and counting. Primary school learners often encounter challenges with reading, ranging from difficulty decoding words to struggles in understanding what they read. Some learners could decode but had trouble comprehending, while others faced difficulties in oral reading despite their ability to decode and understand. These challenges underscored the importance of early intervention and support in fostering strong reading skills during a child's foundational years (Pocare, 2019).

According to Elleman and Oslund (2019), numerous researchers have examined a variety of factors that may influence learners' reading performance. They looked at the receptive vocabulary and reading comprehension abilities of five cohorts of kids who were found to have weak reading comprehension despite having adequate word reading abilities. Children with reading comprehension issues were found to have weaker receptive vocabulary knowledge than their peers across cohorts, albeit this weakness was not as severe as their reading comprehension issue. Additionally, the findings indicated that the observed vocabulary weakness was developmentally delayed, indicating that it is preferable to define it as a correlation rather than a root cause of children's reading comprehension issue

Children who struggle with reading comprehension despite having excellent word reading skills have a shortfall in at least one area of oral language, but this lack does not fully explain how severe their problems are. Overall, reading is a means of exchanging knowledge, ideas, and communication.

When reading becomes a challenge, learners find it more difficult to respond to questions since they don't comprehend the questions. This is why the Department of Education (DepEd) is stepping up its campaign on reading proficiency with the launch of the Hamon: Bawat Bata Bumabasa (3B's) project to close the literacy gap among learners. According to Diosdado San Antonio, Undersecretary for curriculum and instruction, enhancing reading programs will be a top focus (DepEd, 2019). He further emphasized that if the children cannot read, we will never be able to pursue a high standard of education. DepEd's 3Bs initiative encourages offices from central to division level and schools to intensify their reading advocacy to make every learner a reader at their grade level and equip teachers to become effective reading instructors, in light of previous national assessments showing that learners still need to improve their literacy skills (DepEd Memorandum No. 173, s2019).

Teachers find it challenging to teach reading comprehension, and learners find it challenging to learn the skill (Montero, 2019). It is vital to practice reading comprehension because, without it, the author's intended meaning and content are lost (McDonnell, Linde, &

Fredrickson, 2022).

The effects on learners and society of poor literacy and early learning abilities are extensive. The majority of dropouts are children who are behind in kindergarten; their chances of enrolling in a four-year university are fewer than 12%. The multi-year accomplishment disparity that is visible on the first day of kindergarten is not a result of schools. The achievement gap occurs when a child's earliest years are not well-prepared. But after kids start school, they usually continue to fill in the gaps from before kindergarten. Therefore, learners must remain behind.

The problem of reading performance among grade 1 learners at St. Therese de Avila Learning Center was evident, prompting the decision to conduct a research study. Past observations indicated that there were disparities in the reading abilities of students within the same grade level, with some struggling to grasp basic reading concepts while others excelled. Consequently, the decision was made to undertake a comprehensive study to evaluate the reading performance of grade 1 learners, identify specific areas of difficulty, and develop tailored interventions to improve reading outcomes for the learners.

The study aimed to evaluate the reading performance of grade 1 learners at St. Therese de Avila Learning Center. Its goal was to generate an action plan based on the findings to address the varying levels of reading performance among the learners. Through comprehensive assessment and analysis, the study sought to identify specific areas of strength and weakness in reading skills among grade 1 learners.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the levels of reading performance and their contribution to the academic performance of the learners at St. Therese de Avila Learning Center, SY 2023-2024. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex; and
 - 1.3. grade level?
2. What is the assessment of the learners' reading performance?
3. What is the academic performance in English of the learners during 2nd Quarter of the School Year 2023-2024?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the assessment of the learners' reading performance and their academic performance in English?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the learners' profile and their academic performance in English?
6. Which of the assessments on the learners' and respondents' profile significantly predict the effects of their academic performance in English?
7. What action plan can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Methodology

Research Design

The study used descriptive–correlational research design. Descriptive research was used in describing the demographic profile in the performance in English in Grades I learners. It is also correlational research since the demographic profile of the respondents was correlated with their performance in English in terms of reading performance. The researchers identified the reading performance of the learners and how these results affect the learners' academic performance in the English subject.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were Grade 1 learners of St. Therese de Avila Learning Center who were enrolled during the school year 2023 – 2024. There were 43 learners, with approximately 21 males and 22 females included in the study.

Instrument

The instrument used in this study was a structured test questionnaire adopted from Read Theory (2024) consisting of standardized reading passages. These questionnaires consisted of two parts that determined the levels of reading performance and their effect on the achievement of the learners in English subjects.

The first part covered the demographic profile of the learners, which consisted of the following information answered by the respondents. This comprised the Name, Age, Sex, and Grade Level. The second part of the instrument used was the structured questionnaire.

Procedure

To obtain the data needed for the study, the researcher wrote a letter for permission to conduct a study in St. Therese de Avila Learning Center that involved the grades 1 learners as the respondents of the study. The researcher then disseminated permission letters to all respondents' parents that explained the nature and purpose of the study. In the conduct of distributing the questionnaire to the

respondents, the researcher will personally distribute the questionnaires.

Upon distribution, the researcher discussed the purpose of the said survey questions, emphasizing that the result of the study served as the basis for possible recommendations for the action plan for the learners. In addition, the researcher assured the respondents that all their responses were to be treated with extreme confidentiality and had nothing to do with their academic performances.

After establishing the distribution of the questionnaires, each selected respondent was given two sets of documents containing a demographic profile sheet and questionnaires. Clear instructions on how to answer the two documents were provided to the respondents, encouraging them to ask questions about items they found difficult to understand. For the reading performance questionnaire, each respondent read aloud the passages and answered the comprehension questions orally. Lastly, all the documents were collected back by the researchers and kept for data analysis.

Data Analysis

The following techniques were employed to answer the different problems presented.

For problems 1, 2, and 3, Frequency and Percentage, Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the assessment of the learners in terms of their reading performance and also, the respondents' profile based on their academic performance in English.

For problems 4, 5, and 6, Linear Regression was used to determine if there are significant relationships between academic performance, learners' reading performance, profile, and assessment of reading performance.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the gathered data which are presented in descriptive and tabular form. The results and discussion answer the statement of the problem presented in the previous chapter.

Problem 1: What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of age, and sex?

Table 1. *Age of the Respondents*

<i>Age (in years)</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
6	21	48.8
7	20	46.5
8	2	4.7
Total	43	100.0

Table 1 displays the distribution of respondents based on their age in a survey or study. The data reveals that the majority of participants, constituting 48.8%, fall into the age group of 6 years. Following closely, 46.5% of the respondents are 7 years old. In contrast, a smaller proportion, only 4.7%, belong to the 8-year age category. This table served as a concise summary of the age distribution within the sample, illustrating the predominance of 6 and 7-year-olds and the relatively limited representation of 8-year-olds in the surveyed population.

The purpose of this study was to examine age-related differences in the daily attention patterns of first-grade learners. The importance of this study comes from the need to understand attention and apply the information. In addition to altering daily fluctuations, age also affects how interindividual differences in daily fluctuations are distributed, with the greatest variations occurring in children between the ages of 5-7.

Table 2. *Sex of the Respondents*

<i>Sex</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	21	48.8
Female	22	51.2
Total	43	100.0

Table 2 outlines the sex distribution of the respondents in the study, providing a snapshot of the sample's composition. The data shows a nearly equal split between male and female participants, with 48.8% being male and 51.2% female. To guarantee diversity in the sample and enable a more thorough comprehension of any ensuing findings, equal gender representation is crucial.

This suggested that the Department of Education's Philippine K-12 program's age requirement is precisely the same as the average age requirement for responses at each grade level. According to DepEd, Department Order (DO) 020, s. defines the policy on the stringent implementation of the kindergarten cut-off age. 2018 or the DepEd Order No. 47, Section Amendment. 2016.

In the Philippines, elementary education spans six years, from classes 1 through 6 (ages 6 to 12). Before the K-12 reforms were implemented; the sole required component of the basic education cycle was elementary schooling. But because of the changes, compulsory schooling has grown and is now needed for every academic year, through and including grade 12 (Macha et al., 2018).

There was also the desire the check the teachers' own biases criteria and general reliability when grading. Nonetheless, the findings concerning sex were originally so significant (although in the predicted directions) that it appeared that this component merited extra

consideration. Studies have consistently shown that girls have some advantage over boys when it comes to reading performance.

Problem 2: What is the assessment of the learners' reading performance?

Table 3. *Assessment of the Learners' Reading Performance*

Actual Score	Performance Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
27-30	Outstanding	38	88.4
23-26	Very Satisfactory	5	11.6
15-22	Satisfactory	0	0.0
<15	Less Satisfactory	0	0.0
Total		43	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 28.60 (1.31)

Table 3 provides a comprehensive overview of the assessment results for learners in reading performance, presenting both the actual scores and corresponding reading performance levels. The majority of respondents, constituting 88.4%, achieved scores in the range of 27-30, categorizing their performance as "Outstanding." A smaller proportion, 11.6%, falls into the "Very Satisfactory" range, with scores ranging from 23 to 26. Notably, no respondents scored within the "Satisfactory" or "Less Satisfactory" in reading performance among respondents. In addition to the overall number of respondents (43), the table offers other statistical details like the standard deviation (1.31) and mean score (28.60).

Article XIV of the 1987 Constitution emphasized education as being one of the fundamental components in the process of building a nation and a community. This statute mandates that the state provide universal access to high-quality education. Thus, one of the most crucial aspects of school is reading.

The assessment results implied a strong foundation in reading performance among the learners, but educators must maintain a proactive approach to support ongoing growth and development in this critical skill area.

Problem 3: What is the academic performance in English of the learners during 2nd Quarter of the School Year 2023-2024?

Table 4. *Academic Performance in English of the Learners*

Academic Grade	Performance Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
90-100	Outstanding	35	81.4
85-89	Very Satisfactory	8	18.6
80-84	Satisfactory	0	0.0
75-79	Fairly Satisfactory	0	0.0
Total		43	100.0

Note: Mean (SD) = 91.70 (3.08)

Table 4 displays a comprehensive breakdown of the academic performance in English among the learners, categorizing their grades into different reading performance levels. The majority of respondents, comprising 81.4%, achieved outstanding academic grades falling within the range of 90-100. A smaller proportion, 18.6%, falls into the "Very Satisfactory" category, with grades ranging from 85-89. The fact that no students fall into the "Satisfactory" or "Fairly Satisfactory" categories is noteworthy and highlights the high degree of academic performance in English that the examined group possesses overall.

The table also includes the total number of respondents (43) and provides additional statistical details, such as the mean grade (91.70) and standard deviation (3.08). The aforementioned measurements facilitate a thorough comprehension of the English proficiency of the learners and offer significant perspectives for educators, policymakers, and researchers that aim to customize teaching approaches to address certain academic requirements. The high mean grade suggests a generally strong performance across the sample, further highlighting the proficiency of the learners in the English subject.

Reading proficiency was essential for academic achievement. Among the most crucial abilities for any student to acquire is this one. Every academic discipline had prerequisites. It acts as a gateway for all students to dive into various fields since a student who struggles with reading might additionally have difficulties in other subject areas. (Tomas and others, 2021).

Problem 4: Is there a significant relationship between the assessment of the learners' reading performance and their academic performance in English?

The findings of a straightforward regression analysis evaluating the connection between students' academic achievement in English and their reading abilities are displayed in Table 5. The constant term has an estimate of 29.224 with a standard error of 3.876, yielding a significant t-value of 7.540 (p-value < 0.001). Similarly, the performance score predictor has an estimate of 2.184 with a standard error of 0.135, resulting in a highly significant t-value of 16.135 (p-value < 0.001). Both variables are marked as significant at the 0.05 level, indicating a robust relationship. The R-squared score of 0.864 indicates that learners' performance accounts for about 86.4% of the variance in academic performance in English.

These findings suggest a substantial and favorable correlation between students' reading comprehension scores and their academic achievement in English. The significant constant term suggests that even without considering comprehension scores, there is a baseline

academic performance that contributes significantly. The reading performance score predictor's high t-value and low p-value indicate that as reading performance scores increase, academic performance in English is expected to rise significantly. The substantial R-squared value highlights the effectiveness of the model in explaining the variation in academic performance.

Table 5. *Linear Regression Analysis of Academic Performance in English on Assessment of the Learners' Reading Performance*

Predictor	Estimate (B)	S.E.	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Constant	29.224	3.876	7.540	.000	Significant
Comprehension Score	2.184	.135	16.135	.000	Significant

Note: Analysis is based on Linear Regression Analysis

*significant at .05 level

R-squared=.864

These findings suggest a substantial and favorable correlation between students' reading comprehension scores and their academic achievement in English. The significant constant term suggests that even without considering comprehension scores, there is a baseline academic performance that contributes significantly. The reading performance score predictor's high t-value and low p-value indicate that as reading performance scores increase, academic performance in English is expected to rise significantly. The substantial R-squared value highlights the effectiveness of the model in explaining the variation in academic performance.

Educators and policymakers can leverage these findings to develop targeted interventions aimed at enhancing reading performance, ultimately positively impacting students' English academic achievement. It underscores the importance of reading performance as a key predictor of performance is explained by the learners' profile variables included in the model.

The results implied that gender significantly influences academic performance in English, with females exhibiting higher performance on average. However, age does not appear to be a significant predictor in this context. These findings have implications for educational interventions, as educators may consider tailoring strategies to address potential gender-based differences in learning or teaching styles. The modest R-squared value suggests that factors beyond those considered in the model contribute to the variability in academic performance in English, prompting further exploration into additional variables that may impact learners' outcomes.

Sarwer and Ghulam (2018) claimed that fluency in the English language may also boost learners' general academic performance. A key component of the learners' academic success in English is their effectiveness in using the language. As a result, learners who are exposed to English early on may have a higher chance of becoming fluent speakers.

Problem 5: Is there a significant relationship between the learners' profile and their academic performance in English?

The findings of a regression analysis examining the connection between different elements in the learners' profile and their academic achievement in English are shown in Table 6. The constant term has an estimate of 81.854, with a standard error of 5.412, resulting in a highly significant t-value of 15.124 (p-value < 0.001). The constant term suggests a significant baseline academic performance in English, independent of other predictors.

Table 6. *Regression Analysis of Academic Performance in English on the Learners' Profile*

Predictor	Estimate (B)	S.E.	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Constant	81.854	5.412	15.124	.000	Significant
Sex (Female)	1.961	.933	2.102*	.042	Significant
Age	1.348	.800	1.684	.100	Not significant

Note: Analysis is based on Regression Analysis

*significant at .05 level

R-squared=.083

Examining individual predictors, the variable "Sex (Female)" has an estimate of 1.961, a standard error of 0.933, and a t-value of 2.102 (p-value = 0.042), indicating significance at the 0.05 level. This suggested that being female is associated with higher academic performance in English. On the other hand, the predictor "Age" has an estimate of 1.348, a standard error of 0.800, and a t-value of 1.684 (p-value = 0.100), indicating no significance. The R-squared value is 0.083, suggesting that only about 8.3% of the variance in academic performance in English is explained by the learners' profile variables included in the model.

The results implied that sex significantly influences academic performance in English, with females exhibiting higher performance on average. However, age does not appear to be a significant predictor in this context. These findings have implications for educational interventions, as educators may consider tailoring strategies to address potential gender-based differences in learning or teaching styles. The modest R-squared value suggests that factors beyond those considered in the model contribute to the variability in academic performance in English, prompting further exploration into additional variables that may impact students' outcomes.

Reading performance is critical to children's academic success and should be considered when striving to improve their overall achievement. According to a study by Susanti & Irmadila (2018), there is a strong link between academic success in English classes and learners' reading comprehension. It was also more likely that pupils who did well in the reading comprehension test would have high academic success in English.

This study was required in the first place because reading proficiency is important in determining academic achievement and since there haven't been enough studies done on the subject, particularly at the lower elementary level of schooling. Although little research

has been done on reading competency in industrialized nations, there is currently no published data linking reading proficiency to children's academic achievement. Therefore, this study looked at the following: (a) the relationship between reading proficiency and academic performance among lower primary school students after adjusting for the effects of parental involvement, financial situation, and age of the students; (b) the differences in reading proficiency and academic performance between students attending public and private schools; and (c) the differences in reading proficiency and academic performance between male and female students.

Problem 6: Which of the assessments on the learners' and respondents' profile significantly predict the effects of their academic performance in English?

Table 7. *Regression Analysis of Academic Performance in English on the Learners' Profile and Assessment of Reading Performance*

Predictor	Estimate (B)	S.E.	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Constant	29.768	4.108	7.246	.000	Significant
Sex (Female)	.427	.381	1.120	.269	Not significant
Age	.050	.327	.154	.879	Not significant
Comprehension Score	2.146	.145	14.822***	.000	Significant

Note: Analysis is based on Regression Analysis ***significant at .001 level R-squared=.858

Table 7 shows the results of a multiple regression analysis examining the relationship between academic performance in English and a combination of learners' profile variables and their assessment of reading performance. The constant term has an estimate of 29.768, a standard error of 4.108, and a highly significant t-value of 7.246 (p-value < 0.001), indicating the importance of this baseline academic performance in English.

Examining individual predictors, "sex (female)" and "age" are both not found to be significant predictors, with estimates of 0.427 (p-value = 0.269) and 0.050 (p-value = 0.879), respectively. This suggests that, when considered alongside comprehension scores, gender and age do not significantly contribute to the variation in academic performance in English in this model.

The "performance score" predictor, with an estimate of 2.146, a standard error of 0.145, and a highly significant t-value of 14.822 (p-value < 0.001), is crucial in this model. This reinforces the findings from Table 5, emphasizing the strong positive relationship between reading performance scores and academic performance in English. The R-squared value of 0.858 indicates that approximately 85.8% of the variability in academic performance in English can be explained by the combination of learners' profile variables and their reading performance scores.

These results implied that, when accounting for performance scores, gender and age do not significantly contribute to predicting academic performance in English. Performance ratings are still a reliable and extremely important predictor, though. This demonstrates how important reading comprehension is to academic success in English. Educators can use these findings to prioritize interventions aimed at improving learners' performance, recognizing it as a key factor influencing overall performance in English.

One essential skill for learning and acquiring knowledge is reading. It has also been demonstrated that reading performance improves academic achievement. However, reading performance scores do not significantly differ between genders. (Susanti & Irmadila, 2018)

Drawing on the main conclusions of the research outlined above, several suggestions were made to enhance the effectiveness of instruction and tactics that can help students overcome obstacles and limitations related to their English language competency and academic achievement in English-related courses.

Problem 7: What action plan can be formulated based on the findings of the study?

Action Plan on Comprehensive English Proficiency Initiative

The Comprehensive English Proficiency Initiative represents a strategic endeavor aimed at bolstering English proficiency among learners within our institution. In an era marked by globalization, mastery of the English language is not merely advantageous but essential for academic achievement, career advancement, and effective communication. Recognizing the pivotal role of English proficiency, our institution is steadfast in its commitment to providing extensive support and resources, ensuring that all learners acquire the language skills requisite for success.

At the core of this initiative lies a collaborative approach involving diverse stakeholders, including teachers, principals, curriculum development teams, assessment coordinators, and learners themselves. Through collective effort, we endeavor to cultivate a nurturing learning environment conducive to the cultivation and refinement of English language skills. By fostering collaboration and inclusivity, we aim to create a supportive ecosystem wherein learners can thrive and flourish.

This action plan delineates a series of important steps and strategies tailored to our objective of augmenting English proficiency among learners. Commencing with a comprehensive needs assessment, we seek to identify areas necessitating improvement in English proficiency. Subsequently, we will implement targeted interventions, including curriculum enhancements, professional development workshops for educators, integration of technology-based learning tools, and establishment of robust progress monitoring and assessment protocols. By proactively addressing potential barriers and adapting our strategies as required, we aspire to realize our

overarching goal of empowering all learners with the English language skills indispensable for success in today's interconnected world.

Conclusions

The study provided a clear picture of notable achievements among learners, showcasing their commendable proficiency in both reading performance and English academic performance. The majority of participants excelled, with a significant percentage achieving outstanding scores in reading performance and outstanding grades in English. The absence of participants in lower performance categories underscores the overall high academic accomplishment within the surveyed group. These findings collectively highlight a cohort of learners who have demonstrated consistent and impressive success, providing valuable insights into their academic prowess and emphasizing the strength of their achievements across both language domains.

Also, the study revealed the critical influence of reading performance on learners' academic performance in English. The findings consistently highlight the strong positive relationship between reading performance and overall success in English, reaffirming the significant role of these skills. This insight emphasizes the importance of targeted interventions and instructional strategies aimed at fostering and enhancing reading performance abilities among learners.

Lastly, while gender appears to have some association with English performance, as indicated in the analysis of profile variables, the impact of age suggests that other factors may play a more prominent role. The study underscores the need for educators and policymakers to consider a holistic approach, recognizing the multifaceted nature of contributors to academic achievement in English. By prioritizing interventions that strengthen reading performance and understanding the context-specific influences of gender and age, educational stakeholders can better support learners in their English language development. These conclusions provide valuable guidance for shaping effective strategies to enhance English proficiency among learners.

Based on the comprehensive findings and conclusions drawn from the study, several recommendations can be made for different stakeholders in the educational domain.

For school administrators, it is recommended to consider integrating targeted reading performance programs within the curriculum, emphasizing a strategic approach that prioritizes the development of these skills. This could involve allocating resources for specialized training for teachers in effective comprehension instruction methods.

Curriculum planners are encouraged to revisit and enhance existing English language programs, ensuring a balanced focus on reading performance. Incorporating gender-inclusive content and activities can contribute to a more equitable learning environment. Moreover, offering flexibility in teaching strategies to accommodate individual differences in learning styles and reading performance can enhance overall language development.

Teachers play a crucial role in the implementation of these recommendations. Educators should adopt learner-centered, differentiated teaching approaches that address the diverse needs of learners. Continuous professional development opportunities focusing on effective performance instruction and gender-inclusive teaching practices can empower teachers to create more supportive and engaging English language classrooms.

For future researchers, this study suggests exploring additional factors that may influence English language proficiency, beyond the scope of gender, age, and performance scores. Investigating socio-economic factors, cultural influences, or the impact of specific teaching methodologies could contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the complexities influencing academic performance in English.

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